

POSTBUCKLING ANALYSIS OF A COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL PANEL WITH FRAMES AND OMEGA STRINGERS

J. Reinoso¹, A. Blázquez^{2*}, F. París²

¹ Institut für Statik und Dynamik, Leibniz Universität Hannover, Germany.

² Group of Elasticity and Strength of Materials, School of Engineering, University of Seville, Seville, Spain.

* Corresponding author (abg@etsi.us.es)

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1 Introduction

Stiffened panels are found in fuselage and wing covers among many other applications. They are constituted by a thin skin on which stringers are attached to. As a consequence of their high specific strength and stiffness, composite materials have become especially attractive to produce them.

From the mechanical standpoint, these structural components are susceptible to present local instabilities at low load levels due to their high slenderness. This phenomenon decreases the actual rigidity of the component, but it does not happen abruptly. The component is still capable to withstand loads higher than this critical load efficiently, showing a reserve of strength and stiffness. In this regard, great efforts are being done to understand the postbuckling behaviour of stiffened panels when they are loaded in compression, shear, mixed load and/or pressure, see [1–8] and the references therein. This research deals with the experimental and the numerical analysis of a composite stiffened panel under compression load. The stringers are Ω -shape co-bonded to the skin. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the roles of the dummy frames and the geometrical imperfections in the structural response. Several FE models have been developed aiming to reproduce properly the actual supporting conditions.

2 Specimen description

The panels under consideration are included within the European Founded ALCAS Consortium [9]. The characteristic dimensions of the skin of the panel are: axial length (L) 2708 mm, curvature radius (R) 1900 mm and arc length (D) 1100 mm. A general sketch of the specimens is shown in Fig. 1, where

additionally the geometric definition of the Omega stringers and the dummy frames transversely disposed can be found. The skin of the panel and the stringers were manufactured using material IMA/M21E. The materials Loctite-Hysol 96695 and aluminum alloy 2024-T42 were employed for the adhesive layer and dummy frames, respectively.

Fig. 1. Geometrical scheme of the panel.

3 Experimental test

The external solicitation applied to the panel consists of a uniform compressive load along the axial direction of the specimen (z -axis in Fig. 1). The panel was located at a test machine which enables the application of compressive, shear or any combination of both, see a schematic representation in Fig. 2. The lower and upper edges of the panel were set into a resin block, denoted as clamping box in Fig. 2, that ensured the uniform transfer of the

Fig. 2. Test machine equipment. (a) General sketch, (b) Detail of the load introduction zone, and (c) Detail of frame rod support system.

compressive action to the specimen. There were two pairs of symmetrically disposed hydraulic pistons along the longitudinal direction of the panel (see Fig. 2a) that in case of the compression test act as lateral guides constraining the displacements normal to the panel surface at these locations. With the aim of achieving the full-barrel structural conditions, a set of hinge-rods bounds dummy frames to a pole located at the cylindrical axis of the panel (see Fig. 2c).

In order to record the structural performance of the panel during the test, the specimen was monitored with 20 unidirectional strain gages oriented along the axial direction of the panel, mounted at the stringers (denoted as S5-S9, see Fig. 3), and a set of

Fig. 3. Gages and rosettes mounted on the specimen.

8 back-to-back multidirectional rosettes located at the central bays (identified as R1-R4 in Fig. 3). A LVDT was used to record the displacement of the mobile extreme.

Additionally, the panel tested had some preliminary damaged zones by means of the inclusion of Teflon plies (simulating delaminations) and afterwards several low-energy impacts were introduced at some locations.

4 Numerical simulations

Finite element (FEM) simulations of the test were carried out with the code ABAQUS. First-order composite shell elements with linear shape functions and reduced integration scheme (S4R in ABAQUS) were selected for the skin and the stringers.

One of the main issues of this work is related to the achievement of structural conditions similar to those corresponding to the rig of the test. Consequently, some of the auxiliary structural components and extra-reinforcement regions of the panel were also considered to be modelled. These additional features are: the transition zones (in pale green in Fig. 1), the reinforced frame (in grey in Fig. 1) and the four dummy frames (in blue in Fig. 1).

The upper edge of the panel (fixed extreme) was idealised by constraining all degrees of freedom, whereas the lower edge uniquely the axial displacement (z -displacement) was allowed. Regarding the lateral guides, constrained radial displacements ($u_r = 0$) were assumed for all points placed at these locations. Indeed, one of the pivotal hot-points of this work deals with the reliable numerical modelling of the structural conditions with regard to the dummy frames. In particular, three different approaches aiming to incorporate their mechanical role were analyzed, see Fig. 4. On the one side, Models 1 and 2 consider their effects by directly imposing boundary constraints ($u_r = 0$ for Model 1, and $u_r = u_\theta = 0$ for Model 2). On the other side, dummy frames are modelled explicitly in Model 3 by means of additional geometrical entities, supporting conditions ($u_r = 0$) being imposed onto their upper flange. It is worth mentioning that in case of Model 3, these entities were related to the panel by means of *TIE constraint, simulating perfect connections between such entities.

The mechanical response of stiffened panels in the postbuckling regime exhibits a high sensitivity with respect to the initial imperfection [6], specifically

Fig. 4. Dummy frames model options.

with respect to those of geometrical signature. In this work the ideal geometry of the numerical model was perturbed using the buckling mode shapes numerically estimated in a precedent analysis. Hence, the perturbation scheme reads [6]:

$$x_i(n) = x_i^o(n) + \sum_{k=1}^{k=M} a_k u_i^k(n) \quad (1)$$

$x_i(n)$ being the perturbed i -coordinate of the node n , $x_i^o(n)$ the ideal i -coordinate of the node n , $u_i^k(n)$ the i -displacement of the node n for the k buckling mode shape, a_k the coefficient associated to mode k , and M the number of buckling modes used for the perturbation. Coefficients a_k may be computed adjusting expression (1) to the actual geometry of the panel. In this work, the actual geometry was not measured, selection of coefficients a_k being commented later on (Section 5.1.).

5 Buckling results

First of all, a buckling analysis of the panel was performed for every modelling option under consideration, in order to know the critical loads of the panel and the corresponding buckling mode shapes (potential $u_i^k(n)$ in eq. (1)). Table 1 presents the ten lowest buckling loads for the models.

Analysing each columns, differences between first and tenth buckling loads are small, 4.5% for Model 1, 1.9% for Model 2, and 3.3% for Model 3.

Mode	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
1	739	675	723
2	742	677	726
3	744	678	728
4	744	679	731
5	746	682	731
6	748	682	733
7	750	686	734
8	751	687	734
9	760	687	746
10	772	688	747

Table 1. Buckling loads [kN].

Comparing columns, Model 2 exhibit lower buckling loads than Model 3, and these are lower than those of Model 1. This issue might be attributed to the fact that the insertion of the kinematic constraint with regard to the circumferential displacements ($u_\theta = 0$) at the dummy frame locations, induces an extra compressive action in the Model 2 because of the Poisson effect. Models 1 and 3 presented significant similarities with regard to the numerical values of the buckling loads and corresponding deformation patterns. In fact, it seems that Model 3 represents an intermediate option between Models 1 and 2.

Figs. 5 to 7 show the radial displacement distribution of the eigenvectors for the three lowest critical loads for the numerical models presented.

Mode shapes are characterized by some half-waves at the areas defined between two adjacent frames and the outermost stringers. Sometimes they are clearly noticeable between frames on the left (see modes 1 and 3 in Fig. 5), other times on the right (see modes 1 and 2 in Fig. 7) and another on the centre area (see mode 3 in Fig. 6), but never neither on two of these areas simultaneously nor in the area between a stringer or a frame and the reinforcement frame.

The number of half-waves was 6 (for low modes) or 7 (for high modes) along the axial direction (z -axis in Fig. 1) between frames, and only one along the circumferential direction between stringers.

In addition, there are some cases whose eigenvector was almost perfectly symmetric respect to the central stringer (see, for example, mode 2 in Fig. 5) or antisymmetric (see, for example, mode 2 in

$P_1 = 739225 \text{ N}$

$P_2 = 741827 \text{ N}$

$P_3 = 743539 \text{ N}$

Fig. 5. Buckling loads for modes 1 to 3 of Model 1 (movable grip on the left).

$P_1 = 675443 \text{ N}$

$P_2 = 677333 \text{ N}$

$P_3 = 678297 \text{ N}$

Fig. 6. Buckling loads for modes 1 to 3 of Model 2 (movable grip on the left).

$P_1 = 723275 \text{ N}$

$P_2 = 726221 \text{ N}$

$P_3 = 728387 \text{ N}$

Fig. 7. Buckling loads for modes 1 to 3 of Model 3 (movable grip on the left).

Fig. 7). In other cases, symmetry or antisymmetry were not perfect (see, for example, mode 2 in Fig. 6).

It is worth mentioning that, because of the high torsional rigidity of the profile generated by the Ω stringers, antisymmetric modes are not predominant, as would occur with blade stringers, [8]. Approximately, half of the modes obtained were symmetric or quasi-symmetric and the other half were more or less antisymmetric.

5 Postbuckling results

5.1. Load-shortening evolution

For the postbuckling analysis the geometry was modified as indicated by eq. (1), using the coefficients and modes shown in Table 2. These coefficients were selected in order to include a maximum perturbation of about 10% of the laminate thickness in each of the areas between frames (this is the reason why mode 10 is used for Model 1 and mode 9 for Model 3 instead of modes 3 and 2 respectively), [10].

Fig. 8 shows the load-shortening correlation between the experimental and the numerical results corresponding to each of the modelling options

Mode	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
1	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002
2	0.0002	0.0002	-
3	-	0.0002	0.0002
4	-	-	-
5	-	-	-
6	-	-	-
7	-	-	-
8	-	-	-
9	-	-	0.0002
10	0.0002	-	-

Table 2. Coefficients a_k selected.

Fig. 8. Load-displacement evolution correlation.

mentioned above. Thus, in this diagram, circle marks identify the experimental evolution measured by a LVDT during the test, whereas continuum lines represent the numerical predictions obtained by the finite element models.

Experimental evolution is nearly proportional up to a load around 750 kN, at which a sudden jump in the displacements, accompanied by a slight decrease of the stiffness, can be clearly appreciated in the experimental data. Notice that this load level is relatively close to the lowest critical loads for Models 1 and 3.

The (numerical) linear evolution corresponding to Model 3 is presented in Fig. 8 (Linear 3). Linear evolutions for Models 1 and 2 are only slightly different and they are not shown.

The non-linear predictions for the three models are represented as Model 1, 2 and 3 respectively. Non-

linear numerical predictions are very close each other, and nearly proportional till 800 kN. Nevertheless, the final load reached by the computational process is different for each model. Model 1 finished for 863.744 kN due to convergence problems, the displacement being 7.408 mm. Maximum numerical load for Model 2 was 828.125 kN, because of convergence problems also, the displacement being 6.998 mm. Finally, Model 3 reached the maximum load (1000 kN) of the analysis, the displacement being 8.782 mm.

The agreement between numerical prediction and experimental data is satisfactory except for load greater than 750 kN, at which the observed displacement jump was not predicted by any numerical model. Moreover, in the work of ref. [8], where stringers were blades, no similar phenomenon is appreciated. Although it could be assigned to the appearance of some kind of damage, no evidence had been recorded during the test.

In order to analyse this fact, Fig. 9 shows the evolution of the incremental stiffness of the specimen along the test. Test values were computed directly from the experimental points in Fig. 8 using:

$$\text{Stiffness} = \frac{\Delta \text{load}}{\Delta \text{displacement}} \quad (2)$$

The initial stiffness of the panel (obtained from the numerical models) is about 119 kN/mm. It agrees reasonably with the experimental one, which is about 130 kN/mm (7.7% greater).

Nevertheless, it is noticeable the decreasing of the experimental value obtained for the incremental

Fig. 9. Experimental evolution of the incremental stiffness during the test.

stiffness (approximately represented by the dashed line in Fig. 9), which is anomalous comparing with the numerical predictions (which are constant).

At $P^* = 480$ kN a mid-kink can be observed in the experimental points and at $P_{cri} = 750$ kN a sudden drop is clearly identifiable (as in Fig. 8) in the experimental values. For this load, numerical predicted stiffness decreasing noticeably.

Summarizing, two main observations can be made to the results shown in Fig. 8 and 9. There is no explanation for the sudden jump in the load-shortening evolution at 750 kN, unless a non-identified damage had happened. The progressive decrease in the stiffness observed may be associated to an initial deformed shape of the panel (including stringers), an effect not able to be captured by these numerical models.

The panel collapsed abruptly at 848.4 kN. The damage regions were characterized by notable skin-stringer debondings and delaminations at the central area of the panel in conjunction with fiber breakages, see Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Photograph of the damage region.

5.2. Strain gage measures

Figs. 11 to 16 show the correlation between numerical predictions and experimental data corresponding to the rosettes placed at the central area of the panel. R2 and R3 reference the rosette (Fig. 3), ‘o’ references that rosette bonded on the outer surface and ‘i’ to that on the inner; A, B and C reference the directions (Fig. 3); finally, M1, M2 and M3 reference the numerical model (Fig. 4).

Fig. 11. Results for direction A at rosettes R2.

Fig. 12. Results for direction A at rosettes R3.

Fig. 13. Results for direction B at rosettes R2.

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Fig. 14. Results for direction B at rosettes R3.

Fig. 15. Results for direction C at rosettes R2.

Fig. 16. Results for direction C at rosettes R3.

Focusing the attention in the experimental data, notice that, in some cases, they show a slight bending effect for low load levels. This was because of the initial imperfection of the panel. It is worth remembering that geometrical imperfections introduced in the numerical models have not any connection to the actual geometry.

Nevertheless, a close adjustment can be appreciated

for loads below $P^* = 480$ kN. For loads between $P^* = 480$ kN and $P_{cri} = 750$ kN small differences are noticed, they being higher for the Model 2. It is noticeable that these load levels coincided with those detected in Fig. 9 and commented in Section 5.1. They can be used to identify three stages: (1) linear evolution, (2) non-linear effects are noticeable, and (3) postbuckling regime.

Experimental buckling load is closely approximated, exhibiting bending dominated states up to collapse. At deep postbuckling stages poorer correlations are encountered. As shown in [7], the main reason for this fact is that initial imperfection considered is not based on the actual geometry of the panel.

Figs. 17 to 19 show the strain evolution for gages A, B, C and D, located at positions S6, S7 and S8 (see Fig. 3).

Numerical evolution of A, B and C strain gages, which are located on the hat of the Omega stringer and in front of it, are hardly affected by the increase of the load above the critical one; D gages being the most affected. The reason for this fact is that, if

Fig. 17. Results for S6 strain gages.

Fig. 18. Results for S7 strain gages.

Fig. 19. Results for S8 strain gages.

imperfections are introduced by combination of buckling modes, the geometry of the stringers being unmodified. This is because low buckling modes only involve deformation in the skin (where D gages are bonded), and the corresponding displacements of the stringers are negligible.

The differences between the experimental evolution of strain gages A and B (specifically for S6 and S7 devices, where it appears from the beginning of the test) are the evidence that stringers were not straight. Thus, numerical model were not able to reproduce the actual behaviour of the panel.

7 Conclusions

Experimental and numerical analyses of a stiffened panel have been presented. The panel had three Omega stringers and three dummy frames. Special attention has been paid to the modelization of the boundary conditions derived from these frames.

The prediction of the buckling load and the load-displacement evolution, which are global parameters, are quite similar for the different models used. However, the predictions of the local effects, strain gages measurements, are deeply affected by the initial imperfections and by the boundary conditions of the models considered.

In any case, the most important conclusion of this work is that, for a specific specimen, boundary conditions, geometry, auxiliary devices, etc. have to be modelled as accurate as it can be if the evolution of that panel is wanted to be followed in the postbuckling regime.

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